

Template - Processing analysis

Template to process all surfaces acquired with the LSM with the 50x/0.75 and 50x/0.95 objectives.

Processing

Identity card			
Name:	MudPlaster2015MEGII_LSM_50x_type1_e_Topo		
Created on:	4/13/2021 11:37:48 AM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	19.51	µm	
Size:	65532	digits	
Spacing:	0.2976	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	MudPlaster2015MEGII...filtered (As 2.500 μm)		
File path:	D:\Dropbox\jmmarreir...0x_type1_e_Topo.sur		
Created on:	4/13/2021 11:37:48 AM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	0.000	μm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	-255.5	μm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	9.921	μm	
Min:	-6.596	μm	
Max:	3.325	μm	
Size:	333304	digits	
Spacing:	0.02976	nm	
NM-points ratio:	6.559 % (590331 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	MudPlaster2015MEGII_...in non-measured points		
Created on:	4/13/2021 11:37:48 AM		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	9.921	μm	
Size:	333304	digits	
Spacing:	0.02976	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Analyses

8. ISO 25178-2 parameters on surface #7

ISO 25178 - Primary surface			
<i>F: [Workflow] Form removed (LS-poly 3)</i>			
<i>S-filter (λs): [Workflow] S-filtered (λs 2.500 μm)</i>			
Height parameters			
Sq	1.252	μm	
Ssk	-1.695		
Sku	7.616		
Sp	3.324	μm	
Sv	6.597	μm	
Sz	9.921	μm	
Sa	0.8887	μm	
Functional parameters			
Smr	0.3584	%	
Smc	1.201	μm	
Sxp	3.485	μm	
Spatial parameters			
Sal	26.98	μm	
Str	0.6196		
Std	65.25	°	
Hybrid parameters			
Sdq	0.2540		
Sdr	2.776	%	
Functional parameters (Volume)			
Vm	0.03532	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vv	1.236	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmp	0.03532	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmc	0.8960	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvc	0.9827	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvv	0.2535	μm ³ /μm ²	

Analyses:

ISO 25178	8.
Furrow	9.
Texture direction	10.
Texture isotropy	11.
SSFA	12.

9. Furrow analysis on surface #7

All furrows are shown.

Parameters	Value	Unit
Maximum depth of furrows	4.977	µm
Mean depth of furrows	0.9857	µm
Mean density of furrows	3530	cm/cm2

10. Texture direction on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
First direction	89.99	°
Second direction	180.0	°
Third direction	135.0	°

11. Texture isotropy on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
Texture isotropy	86.17	%

12. SSFA on surface #7

